

ADC and T₂ signal intensity changes in perihematoma, cortical, and intrahematoma regions of interest in a rat intracerebral hemorrhage model with and without decompressive craniectomy

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September 2009

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1. ABBREVIATIONS

ADC: apparent diffusion coefficient

AQP₄: aquaporin channel

AVM: arteriovenous malformation

BBB: blood brain barrier

CBF: cerebral blood flow

CMRO₂: cerebral metabolic rate of oxygen

DC: decompressive craniectomy

DT: diffusion tensor

DWI: diffusion weighted imaging

ICH: intracerebral hemorrhage

ICP: intracranial pressure

MIP-2: macrophage-inflammatory protein-2

MMP: matrix metalloproteinase

MRI: magnetic resonance imaging

NO: nitric oxide

OEF: oxygen extraction fraction

rADC: relative ADC

ROI: region of interest

rT₂-SI: relative T₂ signal intensity

TE: echo time

TPA: tissue plasminogen activator

TR: repetition time

UP: unadjusted P

2. ABSTRACT

Objective: Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) is associated with high mortality and morbidity rates. The pathologic contribution of secondary ischemia in perihematomal tissues is controversial. No acute treatment of ICH is available, apart from the supportive care. Decompressive craniectomy (DC), however, is a promising treatment modality, and we recently showed that DC improved neurological outcome and mortality in experimental ICH. To further explore the effects of DC on the brain tissue after ICH, we decided to evaluate magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) changes in and around hematoma following DC.

Methods: We used autologous blood injection model to produce ICH in basal ganglia in Wistar rats. We randomly allocated the rats into five groups as: ICH-only (without DC) and three groups of ICH with DC performed at 1, 6, or 24 h, and DC-only group (without ICH). After a baseline MRI on day 0, re-imagings followed on days 3 and 7. We assessed cytotoxic and vasogenic edema. For this, we collected relative apparent diffusion coefficient (rADC) and relative T₂ signal intensity (rT₂-SI) values. Regions of interest (ROIs) included: inner parts of the hematoma, tissues surrounding the hematoma (perihematomal inner and outer layers), and the ipsilateral cortex.

Results: In the ICH-only group, no decreased rADC values were observed in the perihematomal ROIs. In this group, rADC and rT₂-SI values of the cortex showed no changes during the follow-up. rADC was increased in earlier DC groups (1 and 6 h) on day 3 compared to ICH-only group. No increase in rT₂-SI accompanied this finding. Intrahematomal ROI's showed no differences on MRI related to the timing of the DC. Increased rT₂-SI in perihematomal outer ROI was a consistent finding during the follow-up, starting from the baseline imaging and it was further increased on day 3 when DC was performed at 6 h.

Conclusions: We found no evidence of perihematomal ischemic penumbra in the hyperacute phase (day 0) in ICH model. We also suggest that hematoma leads to no secondary injury in the cortex. DC performed earlier than 24 h induced MRI changes suggesting tissue expansion both in perihematomal tissues and the cortex. DC generates

no effect on inner hematoma MRI parameters, thus the composition of the hematoma remains same despite DC.

Key words: Apparent diffusion coefficient, brain, decompressive craniectomy, edema, intracerebral hemorrhage, magnetic resonance imaging, rat, therapy.

3. INTRODUCTION

Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) accounts for 10% of all strokes worldwide. ICH is associated with high mortality and morbidity rates. One year survival is only 40-50% and majority of survivors have chronic disability (Nilsson, O. G. et al. 2002; Vermeer, S. E. et al. 2002). This poor outcome is the result of many factors including direct tissue damage, growing mass effect and a process called edema (Gebel, J. M., Jr. et al. 2002). Furthermore, delayed damage is mediated by toxins from blood and its breakdown products, thrombin, inflammation, and other factors (Lee, K. R. et al. 1996; Xi, G. et al. 2001). Apart from that, other secondary changes such as apoptosis (Matsushita, K. et al. 2000), excitotoxicity (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 2003), and blood brain barrier (BBB) disruption (Power, C. et al. 2003) give a cumulative additional effect to the damage.

For decades, scientists have been debating about the existence and pathophysiological role of perihematomal penumbra. Studies in rats (Deinsberger, W. et al. 1999; Orakcioglu, B. et al. 2008), in primates (Bullock, R. et al. 1988) as well as in humans (Siddique, M. S. et al. 2002; Sills, C. et al. 1996) have shown conflicting results. With the debate going on (Bullock, R. et al. 1988) (Carhuapoma, J. R. et al. 2000) (Deinsberger, W. et al. 1999; Schellinger, P. D. et al. 2003), some experiments has suggested in favor (Kidwell, C. S. et al. 2001) and some against (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 1999; Xi, G. et al. 2001) the presence of the perihematomal penumbra region. Orakcioglu and his colleagues have shown with serial perfusion and diffusion scans on MRI that there is no such region as penumbra in ICH (Orakcioglu, B. et al. 2008). Recently, Zazulia and coworkers have proposed the existence of metabolic penumbra on the basis of glucose uptake (Zazulia, A. R. et al. 2009).

To fight massive brain swelling and consequent tissue destruction, decompressive craniectomy (DC) was successfully implemented in malignant ischemic brain infarction (Vahedi, K. et al. 2007). Thereafter we confirmed the efficacy of DC in an ICH model in rats (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009).

Since DC significantly improved the outcome in hemorrhagic rat model (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009), we decided to analyze the changes in ADC- and T₂ signal intensity in several groups of animals that underwent ICH and DC as well as the temporal changes within the groups. Furthermore, we studied the presence/absence of perihematomal ischemic penumbra.

4. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

4.1 Intracerebral Hemorrhage (ICH)

4.1.1 Epidemiology

ICH results from bleeding into the brain parenchyma. After the onset, bleeding may continue and the hematoma grow for several hours, leading to progressive deterioration of the patient's clinical condition (Brott, T. et al. 1997; Fujii, Y. et al. 1994; Kazui, S. et al. 1996). Urgent emergency procedures and intensive care are often needed. Computed tomography (CT) soon after the onset of symptoms is crucial for the diagnosis. Case fatality is high, as 35–52% of patients die within 30 days and half of the deaths occur in the first two days (Anderson, C. S. et al. 1994; Broderick, J. P. et al. 1993). Up to 58% of survivors have been reported to be functionally independent by 1 year (Hardemark, H. G. et al. 1999).

The incidence of ICH varies geographically, highest incidence of around 20-30% of all strokes are found in Asian and African populations, especially Japan 48/100,000 persons/year (Inagawa, T. et al. 2000) and around 10-15% in western populations. ICH incidence in Finland seems to be somewhat higher, 21 to 31/100,000 persons/year (Fogelholm, R. et al. 1992; Saloheimo, P. et al. 2006). Amongst nontraumatic causes hypertension and cerebral amyloid angiopathy account for 85% of all cases.

4.1.2 Etiology and Risk factors

Arterial hypertension solely accounts up to two thirds of the ICH resulting from bleeding in basal ganglia, thalamus, and brain stem (Brott, T. et al. 1986). Amyloid angiopathy accounts for second most common cause of primary ICH resulting from bleeding mainly in lobar or subcortical areas (Caplan, L. R. 1992; Gilbert, J. J. & Vinters, H. V. 1983; Qureshi, A. I. et al. 2001).

Only 12–18% of all ICH cases are classifiable as the secondary type of ICH (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 2001). The most important causes of secondary ICH are vascular

abnormalities, which carry the risk of rebleeding. Of these the most common anomalies are cerebral arterial aneurysms, arteriovenous malformations (AVM), and cavernous hemangiomas. The secondary causes of ICH are presented in Table 1. The hemorrhage due to a ruptured aneurysm infrequently has a parenchymal component and sometimes extends into brain ventricles but majority around 85% of cases comprises of subarachnoid hemorrhage (van Gijn, J. & Rinkel, G. J. 2001). Arteriovenous malformations are complex vascular formation in which the arteries directly drain into the veins without intervening capillaries and are associated with an estimated mean annual hemorrhage risk of 4% (Hernesniemi, J. A. et al. 2008). Cavernous hemangiomas are low-flow vascular malformations with no feeding arteries or draining veins. The malformation comprises of 1-2% of ICH per year, with epilepsy as the most common presenting sign (Cantu, C. et al. 2005).

Table 1. Causes of intracerebral bleeding

Etiology

Primary ICH (78-88%)

Chronic Hypertension (60-70%)
Amyloid angiopathy (15%)
Idiopathic

Secondary ICH (12-18%)

Non traumatic

Aneurysm (Familial)
Arterio-venous malformation (AVM)
Cavernous Malformation
Brain Tumors
 Primary (Glioblastoma, Hemangioblastoma)
 Secondary (Metastatic tumors)
Coagulopathies
 Anti-phospholipid syndrome
 Disseminated intravascular coagulopathy
 Thrombophilia
 Thrombotic-thrombocytopenic purpura
 Complication of Henoch-Schönlein purpura
 Hepatic and Renal failures
Dural sinus venous thrombosis
Arterio-venous dural fistulas
Hemorrhagic infarct
Vasculitis
Vasculopathies
 Dissection
 Moyamoya
Medications and Drugs
 Anticoagulants
 Illicit drugs
 Cocaine, Ecstasy, Amphetamine
 Thrombolytic
 Antiplatelet drugs
 Sympathomimetic
Honeybee sting
Alcohol

Traumatic

Surgical procedures and interventions

Other Rare causes:

Cerebral venous thrombosis
Cerebral Endometriosis
Polycystic kidney disease
Marfan syndrome
Ehlers Danlos syndrome
Sturge Weber syndrome
Dilated arteriopathy (dolichoectasis)
Convulsions
Pregnancy Toxemia

Chronic hypertension accounts for 50-70% of the risk factors (Rincon, F. & Mayer, S. A. 2004). Other factors includes advanced age, heavy alcohol use, smoking, low serum cholesterol (less than 4.1 mmol/l), and the presence of ε2 and ε4 alleles of the apolipoprotein E gene related to amyloid angiopathy. Less common risk factors (Table 2) include deficiencies of coagulation factors like factor I, VII, VIII, IX, XIII, and von Willebrand factor (Rincon, F. & Mayer, S. A. 2004; Sutherland, G. R. & Auer, R. N. 2006). In addition, male gender, pregnancy, African and Japanese race, use of anticoagulants, antiplatelet drugs, and cocaine are well-recognized risk factors. Cocaine use is one of the most important causes in young patients (Smith, W. S. et al. 2001). There is an age predilection for the occurrence of the disease: below the age of 40 years AVM or cavernomas are the most common single causes (Aminoff, M. J. 2009), whereas between 40 and 70 years the most frequent sources are ruptured perforating arteries (deep hemorrhages), in the elderly amyloid angiopathy is also a common presentation (Smith, W. S. et al. 2001).

Table 2. Epidemiological risk factors

Epidemiological risk factors	Correlation with factors	Age adjusted RR*(Sturgeon, J. D. et al. 2007) or OR**
Age per 10 years	Higher with age	2.06
Sex	More in women than men	1(female),0.87(male)
Ethnicity	More in black and Japanese population	1.89
Non epidemiologic risk factor		
Hypertension(stage II)	Most important	2.71
Alcohol	Higher incidence with abuse	1.17
Smoking	Controversial result	1.29
Hypercholesterolemia	Low cholesterol higher incidence	0.73
Body mass index		0.94
Diabetes	No significant correlation	1.11
	Significant relation	

*RR- Relative risk, **OR- Odds ratios

4.1.3 Pathophysiology of intracerebral hemorrhage

Nontraumatic intraparenchymal primary hemorrhage arises from the rupture of the small penetrating arteries originating from the anterior cerebral artery, middle cerebral artery, posterior cerebral artery, and the basilar artery. They are mainly affected by degenerative changes associated with hypertensive arteriosclerosis or amyloid angiopathy. Direct tissue destruction and dissection of blood along tissue planes occur, followed by edema formation and ICP (intracranial pressure) increase. Delayed damage can be mediated by toxins associated with blood breakdown products, thrombin, leukocyte infiltration, and apoptosis. Predilection sites for ICH include the basal ganglia (35-44%), thalamus (10-25%), pons (5-9%), cerebellum (5-10%), neocortex (19-25%), and other brainstem sites (1-5%) (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 2001; Sutherland, G. R. & Auer, R. N. 2006). Following texts describes the various injury mechanisms in detail.

4.1.3.1 Hematoma growth

A prospective study demonstrated early hematoma growth in 103 patients with 38% growth within 3 hours from ICH onset in more than one third of the patients, with two third of the patients already showing hematoma growth 1 hour following baseline imaging (Brott, T. et al. 1997). Origin of hematoma expansion is suggested to be from continuous bleeding from the primary source, mechanical disruption of surrounding vessels (Kazui, S. et al. 1996), local coagulation abnormality, and acute hypertension (Broderick, J. P. et al. 1990; Kazui, S. et al. 1997). Apart from the mass effect, there are secondary changes to surround tissue, including neuroglial cell death due to necrosis and apoptosis (Matsushita, K. et al. 2000; Xue, M. & Del Bigio, M. R. 2000), inflammation, and vasogenic edema due to BBB disruption (Power, C. et al. 2003; Qureshi, A. I. et al. 2003).

4.1.3.2 Perihematoma Penumbra

It is the region proposed to be ischemic from the mass effect of hematoma, edema, and other inflammatory changes. This is the region immediately adjacent to the hematoma so the term “perihematoma penumbra” was proposed based on the experimental (Deinsberger, W. et al. 1999; Mendelow, A. D. et al. 1984; Nath, F. P. et al. 1987) and clinical studies (Siddique, M. S. et al. 2002; Sills, C. et al. 1996) .

Scientific community is divided by the fact that some experiments disproved the perihematomal penumbra (Butcher, K. S. et al. 2004; Carhuapoma, J. R. et al. 2000; Qureshi, A. I. et al. 1999; Schellinger, P. D. et al. 2003; Xi, G. et al. 2001) whereas experiments by Butcher and coworkers (Butcher, K. S. et al. 2004) reported self limited perihematomal oligemia, which normalized after 3-5 days from symptom onset. They reported that the relative apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) value which is the ratio of ADC perihematoma over contralateral regions, independently predicts relative and absolute edema volume and volume of perihematoma is directly proportional to the rate of diffusion, which is incompatible with cytotoxic edema but consistent with edema of plasma origin.

MRI-based studies may be non-reliable, since measurement of diffusion in perihematomal region could be added by the falsely elevated ADC ratio in hemorrhage-related extracellular vasogenic edema, and the falsely depressed ADC ratio in ischemic-related cytotoxic edema. Other factors are hemoglobin and its breakdown products which interfere with the analysis of MRI data.

Human perfusion studies with computed tomography (CT) scans have shown no evidence of perihematomal penumbra (Fainardi, E. et al. 2008; Tayal, A. H. et al. 2007), but showed decreased CBF (Ding, H. Y. et al. 2008). Furthermore positron-emission tomography (PET) studies analyzing cerebral metabolic rate of oxygen (CMRO₂), oxygen extraction fraction (OEF), and CBF reported similar findings like CT scans and showed no signs of ischemia but preserved autoregulation and impaired metabolic rate (Hirano, T. et al. 1999; Powers, W. J. et al. 2001; Zazulia, A. R. et al. 2001). Inflammatory tissue damage, mass effect and clot-related vasogenic edema in growing hematoma results in diaschisis (remote autoregulatory hypoperfusion due to reduced oxygen demand) which is suggested as the reason behind the altered perihematomal perfusion (Schellinger, P. D. et al. 2003).

Mitochondrial impairment was recently reported to be responsible for the reduced metabolic demand in perihematomal penumbra zone (Kim-Han, J. S. et al. 2006). In human studies, the biochemical characteristics of perihematomal penumbra zone has been found to be similar to that of penumbra surrounding traumatic brain contusion (Nilsson, O. G. et al. 2006). Such changes have been found to reverse as soon as surgical hematoma evacuation is done (Kim-Han, J. S. et al. 2006; Verweij, B. H. et al.

2000). Still, the changes observed in traumatic brain injury are suggested to be of mitochondrial rather than ischemic origin (Kim-Han, J. S. et al. 2006; Verweij, B. H. et al. 2000). In addition reactive oxygen species, produced by impairment of mitochondria is likely to play additional role in declining the mitochondrial respiration and leading to oxidative damage (Kim-Han, J. S. et al. 2006).

Other mechanisms have been proposed to play considerable role in the pathogenesis of perihematomal tissue damage, including excitotoxicity, involvement of complement and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) and inflammatory mediators (interleukin-1, interleukin-6, inter-cellular adhesion molecule, tumor necrosis factor-alfa and vascular endothelial growth factor) by activation of leukocytes and platelets. In addition, blood degradation products together with thrombin, fibrinogen, TPA, and clotting factors, have been proposed as a mechanism in perihematomal tissue damage.

Zazulia et al proposed that the tissue immediately surrounding a brain hemorrhage did not exhibit classical ischemia on basis of OEF (Zazulia, A. R. et al. 2001), while continuing their experiment they have recently observed an increased glucose uptake in the immediate perihematomal tissue. This increase in uptake occurred generally between 2 to 4 days after hemorrhage and resolved by 5 to 8 days after hemorrhage (Zazulia, A. R. et al. 2009). This time course is similar to that reported by Bergneider where upregulation of glucose uptake observed by brain PET in traumatic hemorrhage (Bergneider, M. et al. 2000). Regional hyperglycolysis along with changes in neurochemistry (Miller, C. M. et al. 2007) led the authors to describe the region surrounding the ICH as metabolic penumbra.

4.1.3.3 ICH-induced edema

Edema formation around ICH results mainly from the toxic effects of red blood cell or hemoglobin breakdown products (Figure 1), resulting in disruption of BBB and hence contributing to increased cerebral water content in the vicinity of hemorrhage (Xi, G. et al. 2001). Involvement of coagulation cascade cannot be denied as its been found that there is an activation of extrinsic coagulation when there is contact between blood and tissue factors (del Zoppo, G. J. et al. 1992). A 24-hour study by Lee and coworkers found that adding prothrombinase to plasma produced cerebral edema and adding

thrombin inhibitor (Hirudin) prevented from producing edema (Lee, K. R. et al. 1996). Furthermore, same group examined the role of thrombin and the coagulation cascade following injection of blood, artificial clot (composed of styrene microsphere, fibrinogen, and thrombin), and separately the components of artificial clot (Lee, K. R. et al. 1996). Early edema was formed after clotting of the hematoma by exudation of the remaining serum protein into the periphery of the hematoma (Gebel, J. M., Jr. et al. 2002; Xi, G. et al. 2001). Such hyperacute perihematomal edema was reduced by intrahematomal administration of TPA and intrahematomal heparin (Wagner, K. R. et al. 1999).

Figure 1: Mechanisms of edema formation

Adapted from Xi et al 2006 (Xi, G. et al. 2006).

Rat brain water content increases progressively reaching its peak at 48h and 72h and resolving at 7 days following ICH (Zhang, X. et al. 2006). Temporal evolution of experimental perihemorrhagic edema has been described as hyperacute, acute, and late onset (Rincon, F. & Mayer, S. A. 2004; Xi, G. et al. 2006). Hyperacute edema is caused by serum proteins, electrolytes, and glucose. Acute edema is caused by cellular toxicity, humoral toxicity, coagulation cascade, and excitotoxicity and finally late phase is suggested to involve blood degradation products, nitric oxide, free radicals, apoptosis, and MMPs.

Following ICH the upregulation of the AQP4 expression in perihematomal brain reached maximum at 3 to 7 days. Iron overload and AQP4 (aquaporin channel) may play a critical role in the formation of brain edema after ICH (Qing, W. G. et al. 2009). Inflammatory mediators such as neutrophils, cytokines, complements (C3 and CR2), monocytes, and macrophages have been shown to potentiate the edema formation (Zhang, X. et al. 2006). Where as mast cell inhibitors was shown to reduce brain edema and hematoma expansion (Strbian, D. et al. 2007).

4.1.3.4 Inflammation

Another mechanism resulting in progressive brain injury is inflammation resulting from the extravasation of blood and its components namely thrombin, hemoglobin, plasmin, complement, fibrin degradation products, and leukocytes into the brain parenchyma (Xi, G. et al. 2006; Xue, M. M. et al. 2003). The inflammation response starts soon after ICH induction and lasts for days in humans and animals (Gong, C. et al. 2000; Xue, M. & Del Bigio, M. R. 2000).

4.1.4 Surgical and Medical treatment

Symptomatic and supportive management for ICH includes initial management by controlling airway, breathing, circulation, fluid balance, control of body temperature, nutritional support and prevention of complications related to gastrointestinal tract, seizures, infections, pressure sores, and deep venous thrombosis.

4.1.4.1 Surgery

The main cause of mortality and morbidity in ICH patients is due to the mass effect of hematoma (Gebel, J. M., Jr. et al. 2002) and edema. Surgical treatment of ICH by surgical removal of blood clot failed to prove beneficial in surgical trial in intracerebral hemorrhage (STICH) (Mendelow, A. D. et al. 2005). STICH II trial has been started to address the outcome of early surgery in lobar nonaneurysmal ICH without intraventricular hemorrhage (Mendelow, A. D. 2009). However, recently Adeoye and colleagues have challenged the significance of STICH II which accounts for only 7.7%

of all ICH patients (Adeoye, O. et al. 2008). As per European Stroke Organisation in the latest guideline (Steiner, T. et al. 2006), surgery is recommended for superficial hematomas, falling cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP), rising ICP together with deteriorating consciousness level (Mendelow, A. D. & Unterberg, A. 2007).

Other ongoing ICH trials like Clot Lysis Evaluating Accelerated Resolution of Intraventricular Hemorrhage (CLEAR IVH) has given a positive response in phase I and II (Hanley, D. F. 2008), now has entered into phase III trial (Hanley, D. F. 2009). Similarly, Minimal Invasive Surgery In Deep ICH (MISTIE) gave positive results in preliminary phase (Morgan, T. et al. 2008), now is in clinical trial phase (Hanley, D. F. 2009).

To prove the efficacy of surgical decompressive craniectomy (DC) in ICH, we performed decompression surgery in our laboratory after inducing ICH by autologous blood transfusion in rats and found high mortality of 45% in the ICH-only group compared with no death in the DC ICH 1-h and 10% in DC ICH 6-h groups. A corresponding significant worst neurological score was observed in ICH only compared to ICH+DC groups. Similarly behavioral score showed better scores for craniectomy only and ICH+DC groups compared to deterioration in outcome in ICH only group. While ICH volumes showed a significant difference among groups with different timings of craniectomy after allowing for effect of length of follow-up. However, ICH volume on day 3 was significantly larger in the ICH-only group than in any ICH+DC groups (Figure 9). Brain swelling reached its maximum on day 3 in all groups (Figure 11). TUNEL-positive cell count showed a trend in favour of DC, but did not let us to draw any firm conclusion of the DC effects on ICH+DC and ICH-only groups. Overall we observed that the earlier the DC the better the outcome (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009).

4.1.4.2 Medical Management

Osmotic therapy, despite little evidence of its efficacy, is widely used in patients with large ICH and increased ICP. Mannitol is mainly the agent acting as intravascular osmotic agent, thus, may decrease ICP through autoregulation and helps in buying time before surgery (Misra, U. K. et al. 2005).

The role of blood pressure management is controversial. AHA/ASA guidelines recommend to maintain systolic blood <180mmHg and/or mean arterial pressure <130mmHg (Broderick, J. et al. 2007).

Recently in a phase IIb trial, recombinant factor VII was found to reduce rate of clot expansion and improved outcome (Mayer, S. A. et al. 2005). The results of the phase III trial, although consistent with the previous one in terms of dose-related hematoma growth reduction and safety profile, showed no statistical difference between the treated and control groups in terms of clinical efficacy (Mayer, S. A. et al. 2008).

4.1.5 Models of Intracerebral Hemorrhage

The most common sites of human ICH are caudate-putamen, thalamus, cerebellum, and pons. A number of experimental cerebral hemorrhagic models has been developed to study the mechanisms of underlying cerebral bleeding and underlying pathophysiology. The ideal experimental cerebral hemorrhagic model satisfies following criteria: reproducible volume of hemorrhage, hemorrhage mimicking the clinical situation, uniform degree of hemorrhage, easy to perform, and reasonable cost (Tatlisumak, T. & Fisher, M. 2006). Different species of animals including mouse (Clark, W. et al. 1998), rat (Mendelow, A. D. 1993; Rosenberg, G. A. et al. 1990; Sinar, E. J. et al. 1987), cat (Kobari, M. et al. 1988), dog (Coulter, D. M. & Gooch, W. M. 1993), rabbit (Kaufman, H. H. et al. 1985), baboon (Del Zoppo, G. J. et al. 1986), pig (Mun-Bryce, S. et al. 2001), and primates (Bullock, R. et al. 1988) have been used to establish these models. The most commonly used models are autologous blood injection and collagenase injection models. The other uncommon ones are balloon inflation model and a model of avulsion of cerebral blood vessels. Outcomes are measured on the basis of mortality, neurological scores, behavioral tests, dynamics of hematoma and edema growth using MRI, extent of ischemic injury and apoptosis, neuroinflammation, and changes in CBF and ICP.

4.1.5.1 Autologous whole blood-induced ICH in the rat

In this model autologous blood is infused into the brain parenchyma. The favored site of injection is basal ganglia (Deinsberger, W. et al. 1996; Mendelow, A. D. 1993), but

other areas like left frontal lobe (Masuda, T. et al. 1988), paramedian white matter (Cossu, M. et al. 1991), and foreleg area of the motor cortex (Kleiser, B. et al. 1989) have occasionally been used. The volume of blood injected usually varies from 10-100 μ l (Mendelow, A. D. 1993; Nath, F. P. et al. 1986). Volume approaching 100 μ l have shown to induce increased intracranial pressure and complications due to systemic effects (Kingman, T. A. et al. 1988). Experience from our own laboratory suggested that 50-75 μ l of blood injected with a Hamilton syringe into the basal ganglia slowly over 5 minutes results in reasonably good reproductability of hematoma volume (Strbian, D. et al. 2007). We also keep injection rate to 2 μ l per 12 sec and before injecting the blood we slightly withdraw the Hamilton syringe by 0.5mm, producing a small pouch. We keep the needle inserted at the site of injection for another 3 to 5 minutes after injection is completed. This helps in preventing the back flow of injected blood along the needle track. Deinsberger and other scientists have worked with double injection model which is divided in two phases: the first phase of small volume injection followed by an interval of 7 minutes and then second phase of rest of volume injected (Deinsberger, W. et al. 1996). This model has been used in the rat (Hickenbottom, S. L. et al. 1999) and other species (Belayev, L. et al. 2003; Thiex, R. et al. 2003) with success.

4.1.5.2 Bacterial collagenase-induced ICH

Originally introduced by Rosenberg and coworkers, this model of ICH is induced by injection of bacterial collagenase in the basal ganglia (Rosenberg, G. A. et al. 1990). Collagenase acts by breaking down the vascular matrix especially collagen IV resulting in opening of BBB and intraparenchymal bleeding. This model mimics human spontaneous ICH, but is associated with robust local inflammation. Site of injection is usually basal ganglia. Only in swine model it is given in primary somatosensory cortex (Tatlisumak, T. & Fisher, M. 2006). Rosenberg used 0.1 to 1 unit of bacterial collagenase diluted in 2 μ l of saline, with 0.5 unit achieving the desired condition (Rosenberg, G. A. et al. 1990). The hematoma volume correlates with the amount of collagenase injected. In a modification, Del Bigio and coworkers used 0.14 units of collagenase diluted in 0.7 μ l saline with heparin, leading to rapid evolution of hematoma size (Del Bigio, M. R. et al. 1996). Experiments in our laboratory has suggested that 0.37 units of bacterial collagenase diluted in 0.37 μ l saline leads to optimal growth of hematoma (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009). This model gives high reproductability with

volume correlating with the amount of collagenase introduced and uniform shape of hematoma.

4.1.5.3 Balloon inflated model

Sinar and coworkers first used this model to mimic the space occupying effect of hematoma and to study the pathophysiology of ischemic injury after hematoma removal (Sinar, E. J. et al. 1987). In this model, a microballoon mounted in a 25- gauge blunted needle is inserted into the caudate nucleus to a depth of 5.5mm and inflated to 50ul volume over a period of 20 sec with a radiopaque contrast medium and visualized with the help of x-ray. Since the volume given is precise so the hematoma is highly reproducible and of uniform shapes (Tatlisumak, T. & Fisher, M. 2006).

4.1.5.4 Cortical blood vessel avulsion

An infrequently used model, in which the surface cortical blood vessels are avulsed by gently pulling away the leptomeninges (Funnell, W. R. et al. 1990; Xue, M. & Del Bigio, M. R. 2003). The end result was ICH and ischemic infarction making it difficult to compare with other models.

4.2 Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

MRI is based on the principle of nuclear resonance imaging. Initially used mainly by chemists, now widely used in clinical practice. Water molecule has proton ion which becomes magnetized in a magnetic field and starts to rotate in longitudinal and transverse axis. The relaxation time in longitudinal axis is called T_1 relaxation time and relaxation time in transverse axis is called T_2 relaxation time. T_2^* relaxation is transverse relaxation time occurring mainly due to static magnetic field used in all MR imaging. T_1 and T_2 relaxation times differ for different tissues and are expressed in values of milliseconds (ms). Water has the highest T_1 and T_2 relaxation times (Woodward, P. & Freimarck, R. 1995). See Figure 2 for different types of imaging.

Spin Echo

At 90 degree Radio frequency (RF) the resultant transverse signal pattern produced by proton is termed Free induction decay (FID). When a 180 degree RF pulse is introduced the proton's spin is rephased to original. The term echo simply refers to a process by which we can rephase spins that have become unphased (Woodward, P. & Freimarck, R. 1995).

Image weighting

In spin echo imaging, TR and TE determine tissue contrast. Time of repetition (TR) is the amount of time that elapses between 90 degree RF pulses on a given slice or the amount of time we allow individual proton vectors to realign with the main magnetic field. Time of Echo (TE) is the amount of time between 90 degree RF pulse and the measurement of signal echo. Both TR and TE measured in milliseconds (Woodward, P. & Freimarck, R. 1995).

T_1 weighted image

The contrast produced due to the variation produced in the longitudinal relaxation rates. Short TR and TE sequences are required to produce contrast. The short TR allows tissues with short T_1 values to recover faster than compared to tissues with long TR. The short TE allows minimal loss of transverse signal due to T_2 relaxation. To sum up short

TR increases T_1 effects and the short TE reduces T_2 effects (Woodward, P. & Freimarck, R. 1995). Due to the larger longitudinal and transverse magnetization, white matter (lipid rich) has a higher signal and will appear bright on a T_1 contrast MR image. Conversely, water has less longitudinal magnetization prior to a RF pulse, therefore less transverse magnetization after a RF pulse yielding low signal appearing dark on a T_1 contrast image.

T₂ weighted image

The contrast produced due to the variation in the transverse relaxation rates. Long TR and TE sequences are required to produce contrast. The long TR allows tissue to reach full magnetization and long TE leads to controlled loss of transverse signal due to T_2 relaxation. To sum up, long TR reduces T_1 effect and long TE highlights tissues with long transverse relaxation rates (fluid) (Woodward, P. & Freimarck, R. 1995). Water has a very high T_2 constant, therefore has very high T_2 signal and thus appears bright on a T_2 contrast image. Cerebral white matter (fat containing) is less intense than grey matter. Flowing blood (flow effects) and hematomas (hemoglobin and hemosiderin) have a variable signal intensity on MR images.

4.2.1 Diffusion Weighted Image (DWI)

Every molecule has the property to move in random direction according to Brownian motion. In Human tissues, the water molecules are in constant state of random motion owing to their thermal energy. In vivo, the water molecules have to behave according to the dynamics of cellular transport between different sub-compartments of the heterogeneous tissue structures and the presence of non-permeable membrane. The actual diffusion distance is reduced compared to free water. So the path of single water molecule is therefore directly dependent on the structures of its microenvironment. Intracellular compartment contain more molecular obstruction as compared to extracellular compartment, resulting in more diffusion restriction in intracellular compartment compared to extracellular compartment. At the organ level these results in macroscopically visible phenomenon giving the information about the size, orientation, complexity as well as pathological changes in both intra- and extracellular spaces. DWI is based on spin echo sequence with extra encoding process (Roberts, T. P. & Schwartz, E. S. 2007). The short high amplitude gradient pulse is applied between 90 and 180

degree pulse and after the 180 degree refocusing pulse. In the presence of this gradient any molecular displacement occurring during the time between the first and second gradient produces a phase shift of the signal. Due to the very large number of water molecules present in the tissue, the phase shift is distributed reflecting the diffusion-driven displacement distribution, resulting in loss of coherence, and hence, an attenuation of the MRI signal (Pitkonen, M. 2008).

4.2.2 Apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC)

ADC is determined by DWI sequence, and this value is dependent on a number of variables including time, orientation of the imaging plane, tissue being imaged, and the energy state of the tissue (Baird, A. E. & Warach, S. 1998). On ADC maps, brain tissue with low ADC values appears relatively hypointense as compared to the hyperintense signal from tissue with higher ADC values. Rapid onset ischemia produces hyperintense signal on DWI from the region of ischemia leading to decline in ADC values. This lowering of ADC values are related to reduction in cerebral blood flow, energy metabolism breakdown as well as reduction of extracellular water by a shift into the cells leading to cytotoxic edema (Duong, T. Q. et al. 1998; Hoehn-Berlage, M. et al. 1995; Verheul, H. B. et al. 1994). Though ADC values are not specific for ischemia but changes with global ischemia, hypoglycemia, spreading waves of cortical depression, and status epilepticus also lead to decreased ADC values. A rADC value below 0.9 is considered related to cytotoxic edema and whereas rADC above 1.1 is considered as vasogenic edema (Schellinger, P. D. et al. 2003).

4.2.3 Diffusion Tensor imaging (DTI)

Normally when diffusion gradient is applied along the horizontal axis, the signal becomes sensitive only to horizontal motion. However when measured inside living system with three-dimensional structure diffusion sometimes appears to have directionality (Mori, S. 2007). As diffusion is a three-dimensional process, molecular mobility may not be equal in all directions and when it is mapped on DWI, it is called as diffusion anisotropy. Diffusion anisotropy was first observed in brain white matter (Moseley, M. E. et al. 1990). It is still not understood why white matter produces anisotropy, but most investigators believe that myelin sheath plays a contributory role

by enhancing the diffusion of water molecules along the white matter tracts, whereas diffusion along myelin sheath is restricted. In addition, physiological processes such as axolemmic flow, extracellular bulk flow, capillary blood flow and intracellular streaming, may also contribute to white matter anisotropy (Nomura, Y. et al. 1994; Wimberger, D. M. et al. 1995). Nowadays, diffusion anisotropy provides unique in vivo information about white matter structural anatomy and cerebral connectivity (Roberts, T. P. & Schwartz, E. S. 2007). We need at least six different parameters to construct DT maps.

Figure 2: MR images of rat brain with ICH in coronary plane at days 0, 3, and 7.

5. AIMS OF THE STUDY

The aims of this study were to test the hypothesis whether perihematomal penumbra exists in ICH model, and to examine the effects of DC on ADC and T₂ parameters on MRI.

Specific questions elucidated in this experiment include:

- Whether perihematomal ischemic penumbra exists?
- Does DC effects the ADC and T₂ parameters in the perihematomal tissue?
- Does DC has an effect on the cortical tissue?
- How does hematoma changes over time in ICH only group and ICH+DC groups and is there any effect of DC on hematoma resolution?

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All experiments were carried out in Biomedicum Helsinki. The animal research committee approved all studies.

Animals. We used adult male Wistar rats (Harlan Nederland, Horst, The Netherlands), weighing 290 to 340 grams. Before and during the experiments, the rats were housed under diurnal lighting conditions and allowed free access to food and water. Rats were randomly allocated to 5 groups. The animals in groups having the craniectomy at 6 and 24 hours after ICH induction were re-anesthetized before the procedure.

Anesthesia. Animals were anesthetized with an intraperitoneal injection of ketamin hydrochloride (50 mg/kg, Ketalar, Parke-Davis, Sweden) and a subcutaneous injection of medetomidine hydrochloride (0.5 mg/kg, Domitor, Orion, Finland).

Measurement/monitoring of physiological parameters. A PE-50 polyethylene tube was inserted into the left femoral artery for continuous monitoring of blood pressure (Olli Blood Pressure Meter 533, Kone Oy, Espoo, Finland) and for obtaining blood for ICH induction. Rectal temperature was maintained at 37 °C during the operation and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with a heating blanket and a thermo-regulated heating lamp. Bodyweight was measured daily. At the end of the experiment, the femoral catheters were removed and operation wound sutured. Proper analgesic and antibiotic medication was given from time to time to prevent any pain or infection.

Cardiac perfusion and tissue handling. On day 7 after recordings, animals were re-anesthetized with an intraperitoneal injection of 120mg of pentobarbital sodium (Mebumat, Orion, Turku, Finland) and cardiac perfusion was performed. Shortly after cessation of respiration, the chest was opened, a catheter was inserted into aorta via the left ventricle while the heart was still beating, and 200ml of ice cold 0.9% saline was infused at 100 mmHg inflow pressure into the arterial vascular system. Right atrium was incised open just before the saline infusion was initiated to allow all blood to drain. After cardiac perfusion, the brains were quickly removed and dissected coronally into six 2-mm-thick slices with a standard brain-cutting matrix. Thereafter tissues were preserved in formalin for further studies.

ICH model. To mimic ICH, we used the autologous whole blood injection model described elsewhere (Strbian, D. et al. 2008). The head of the animal was fixed into a stereotaxic frame (Stoelting Co., Illinois, USA) and a midline scalp incision was made to disclose the calvarium of the skull. A burr hole 1mm in diameter was drilled on the right side of the cranium: 0.2 mm anterior and 3.0 mm lateral to the bregma. A 27-gauge needle attached to a Hamilton syringe was inserted into the core of the right basal ganglia (at 6.0 mm depth from the skull surface), and 75 μ l of freshly collected homologous arterial blood was injected slowly into the brain (2 μ l per 12 seconds), after which the needle was kept in place for 5 minutes. The burr hole was sealed with bone wax, and the scalp was sutured. We injected 75 μ l of blood, which we found (in a pilot project) to have a mortality rate of approximately 50%, i.e. similar to clinical situation (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009).

Decompressive craniectomy. We utilized DC procedure as described in the classic experimental study with decompressive craniectomy after malignant ischemic stroke (Forsting, M. et al. 1995). Under general anesthesia and after lidocaine application to the bony surface of the skull, a bone flap (0.9 x 0.5 cm) was created in the temporal bone using a dental drill, and additional bone was removed down to the floor of the middle fossa under microscopic control using microscissors. The dura covering the frontal, parietal, and temporal lobes was then opened in a large cruciate incision. No cortical resection of brain was seen (Figure 3). At the end of the procedure, the temporalis muscle and skin flap were adapted and sutured in place. Instruments were kept sterilized and sterile working conditions were followed. Antibiotic ceftriaxon (50 mg/kg, Ceftriaxon Copyfarm, Denmark) was administered subcutaneously immediately

and 24 hours following craniectomy or ICH induction and analgesic buprenorphine (0.05 mg/kg, Temgesic, Schering-Plough, New Jersey, USA) was given subcutaneously three times per day during the first 48 hours.

Figure 3. Representative MRI scan

A) Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) at the level of the basal ganglia in the right hemisphere immediately after ICH induction (T_2^* -weighted imaging). B) The same animal's brain image after decompressive craniectomy, 72 hours after ICH. C) After 7 days.

MR imaging. MRI studies were performed immediately after ICH induction and on days 3 and 7 with a 4.7 T scanner (PharmaScan, Bruker BioSpin, Germany) using a 90 mm shielded gradient that is capable of producing maximum gradient amplitude of 300 mT/m with 80 μ s rise time. A linear birdcage RF coil with an inner diameter of 38 mm was used. After shimming and scout images, coronal T_2^* -weighted images, and DT images were acquired.

T_2^* -weighted images were acquired with a FLASH (Fast Low Angle Shot) sequence (TR=350 ms, TE= 10 ms, flip angle=40, matrix size= 256x128, field of view = 25x25 mm, number of averages = 4, 14 slices, slice thickness= 1 mm).

DT images were acquired using a multi-shot echo-planar spin-echo sequence with 30 diffusion-encoding directions (TR = 3000 ms, TE = 35 ms, Δ = 20 ms, δ = 4 ms, b = 0 and 1500, s/mm^2 , average = 2, matrix size = 128 x 128, field of view = 40 x 40 mm, single slice, slice thickness = 2.0 mm)

MR image-Analyses

The regions of interest were first manually drawn on the epi-DT images with $b = 0$ (T_2 weighted image). The slide selected had the maximum hematoma. In those cases where hematoma was near to the ventricle, we outlined only the lateral part of the perihemorrhagic area. The ROIs are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. ROIs used in the experiment

c1: cortical ROI 1, c2: cortical ROI 2, c3: hypo-intense hematoma, h: hyper-intense hematoma, p1: inner perihematoma, p2: outer perihematoma, m1 and m2: respective mirror or cortical ROI, m3: mirror for hematomal ROI.

T_2 -Signal intensity was calculated from T_2 -weighted image. ADC maps were constructed and ROIs were superimposed on ADC maps to get the values corresponding to region of interest.

We measured the ADC and T_2 -Signal intensity values from ROIs and their corresponding mirror ROIs on the contralateral hemisphere and calculated it as:

$$\text{Relative value} = \text{ipsilateral} / \text{contralateral}$$

7. STATISTICAL ANALYSES

We used a standard software package (SigmaStat 3.1) for statistical analysis. Multiple group comparisons were performed using two way repeated measure analysis of variance (RM-ANOVA) followed by the post hoc Holm-Sidak test. This analysis tests

main effects for treatment and time, and the interaction terms for DC* time and days of follow-up. The $p < 0.05$ level was used to assess statistical significance.

8. RESULTS

Main results are described in the following text. Post hoc all pairwise multiple comparison results are resumed in Table 3.

Table 3. *Only significant Unadjusted P values are presented.

Post hoc results*													
rADC and Signal intensity ratio		p1		p2		c1		c2		c3		h	
		rADC	SI ratio	rADC	SI ratio	rADC	SI ratio						
Comparisons for factor: days of follow up within ICH-only													
0.000 vs. 3.000										0.001	0.02		0.003
0.000 vs. 7.000					0.002					0.002	0.002		
3.000 vs. 7.000					0.024								
Comparisons for factor: days of follow up within ICH-1hr													
0.000 vs. 3.000		0.012		0.003						0.001	<0.001	0.011	0.01
0.000 vs. 7.000					0.021		0.01			<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
3.000 vs. 7.000		0.002		0.001	0.005								
Comparisons for factor: days of follow up within ICH-6hr													
0.000 vs. 3.000		0.01	<0.001	0.003	<0.001					<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
0.000 vs. 7.000										<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
3.000 vs. 7.000			0.006		<0.001								
Comparisons for factor: days of follow up within ICH-24hr													
0.000 vs. 3.000		0.005		0.001			0.005			<0.001	0.001	0.017	0.001
0.000 vs. 7.000		0.001		0.004	<0.001					<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.003
3.000 vs. 7.000					0.007		0.003						
Comparisons for factor: DC time within day 0													
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-only													
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-only													
ICH-24hr vs. ICH-only													
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-24hr													
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-24hr													
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-1hr													
Comparisons for factor: DC time within day 3													
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-only				0.006				0.002					
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-only			0.003		<0.001	0.007		0.007					
ICH-24hr vs. ICH-only							0.003						
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-24hr					0.009								
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-24hr													
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-1hr					0.001								
Comparisons for factor: DC time within day 7													
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-only													
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-only													
ICH-24hr vs. ICH-only		0.008		0.008									
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-24hr													
ICH-1hr vs. ICH-24hr		0.009											
ICH-6hr vs. ICH-1hr													

See Fig 4 legends for ROIs name.

Perihematomal penumbra inner layer-P1-rADC (Figure 5)

Significant difference ($P = <0.001$) appeared among groups for different days of follow-up. Day 3-values were the highest ($UP = <0.001$ day 3 vs day 0 and $UP = 0.006$ day 3 vs day 7). Only in ICH-24h group day 3 and day 7 data were similar.

Figure 5. Perihematomal penumbra (PHP) inner-P1 rADC and rT₂-SI changes with days of follow up.

Perihematomal penumbra inner layer-P1-rT₂-SI (Figure 5)

We found a significant effect of DC time ($P = <0.001$) on this parameter. rT₂-SI values show a trend towards an increase on day 3 and decrease on day 7.

Perihematomal penumbra outer layer-P2-rADC (Figure 6)

The effect of DC time was nonsignificant ($P = 0.053$), whereas the follow-up time emerged as a significant factor ($P = <0.001$). Day 3-values were the highest ($UP = <0.001$ day 3 vs day 0 and $UP = 0.001$ day 3 vs day 7). rADC changes during follow-up were relatively small in the ICH-only group.

Figure 6. PHP outer-P2 rADC and rT₂-SI changes with days of follow up.

Perihematomal penumbra outer layer-P2-rT₂-SI (Figure 6)

Concerning the effect of DC time, significant difference ($P = 0.023$) was observed between ICH-6h and ICH-1h groups ($UP = 0.0053$). In addition, day 3 data appeared different from those of day 7 ($UP < 0.001$) and day 0 data from those of day 7 ($UP < 0.001$). Day 3 signal intensity ratios were increased in the ICH-1h and ICH-6h groups compared to corresponding day 0 values. On the other hand, in the ICH-only and ICH-24h groups, the signal intensity ratios decreased progressively throughout the follow-up.

Cortical-C1-rADC (Figure 7)

An overall significant difference ($P = < 0.001$) appeared due to the effect of DC time. Post hoc assessment indicated the differences between ICH-1h and ICH-only groups

(UP <0.001) and between ICH-6h and ICH only groups (UP <0.001). In addition, there was significant difference in rADC values among different days of follow-up (P = 0.012) (post hoc, UP = 0.0055, day 7 vs day 0; and UP = 0.024, day 3 vs day 0). Slight increase in rADC occurred by time in all the DC groups, with early craniectomy causing a larger increase.

Figure 7. Cortical-C1 rADC and rT₂-SI changes with days of follow up.

Cortical-C1-rT₂-SI (Figure 7)

Significant difference appeared among groups for different days of follow-up ($P = 0.008$) (post hoc, $UP = 0.003$, day 3 vs day 0; and $UP = 0.022$, day 7 vs day 0). There were many slight differences in different directions in an unpredictable pattern. To resume, DC made no change by time and follow up, implying there is no cortical edema.

Cortical-C2-rADC (Figure 8)

Compared to previous result a significant difference ($P = 0.004$) observed due to effect of DC time. Post hoc analysis indicating the difference between ICH -6h and ICH-only ($UP = 0.0016$), and ICH-1h and ICH-only ($UP = 0.0027$). All DC groups showed similar baseline rADC values to that of the ICH-only group, but these were increased significantly on day 3 (Table 3)

Figure 8. Cortical-C2 rADC and rT_2-SI changes with days of follow up.

Cortical-C2- rT₂-SI (Figure 8)

Similarly a significant difference ($P = 0.030$) was observed between days of follow-up and post hoc (UP = 0.00877) in day 7 vs day 0, however, day 3 and day 0 differences were not significant. There were many slight differences in different directions in an unpredictable pattern. There is no cortical edema.

Hematoma Hyperintense-H- rADC

Concerning the effect of follow-up, significant difference ($P = <0.001$) was found (post hoc UP <0.001 day 7 vs day 0, UP <0.001 day 3 and day 0, and UP = 0.043 day 7 vs day 3). Baseline group rADC values were similar, but were increased at each time-point, remaining different from each other.

Hematoma hyperintense-H-rT₂-SI

Significant difference ($P = <0.001$) appeared among groups for days of follow-up. Both day 3 (UP <0.001) and day 7 (UP <0.001) data were different from those of day 0. Signal intensity ratios were increased on day 3 and afterwards decreased on day 7 in all the DC groups, suggesting non- relevance of DC timing on this parameter.

Hematoma hypointense-C3-rADC

We found a significance ($P = <0.001$) concerning the effect of follow-up days. Day 3 (UP <0.001) and day 7 (UP <0.001) data were different from those of day 0. rADC values increased on days of follow-up on DC time.

Hematoma hypointense-C3-rT₂-SI

A significant effect of days of follow-up was found ($P = <0.001$). Day 0 data appeared different from those of day 3 (UP <0.001) and day 7 (UP <0.001). Groups were not different from each other, suggests craniectomy had no effect on hematoma change.

Figure 9. Temporal changes of intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) volumes (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009)

Baseline ICH volume was similar among all groups ($P=0.45$). Although the final ICH volume was somewhat larger in the ICH-only group compared with the ICH-craniectomy groups, this difference was not significant ($P=0.065$). ICH volume at day three was significantly larger in the ICH-only group compared with all of the ICH-craniectomy groups ($P<0.001$).

Figure 10. Herniation in the ipsilateral side of ICH on day 3 after DC at 6h.

Figure 11. Temporal changes of hemispheric expansion (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009)

9. DISCUSSION

Currently, no medical (Mayer, S. A. et al. 2008) or surgical (Mendelow, A. D. & Unterberg, A. 2007) modalities are available to treat ICH, except for general supportive care. The efficacy of DC in stroke was first described in experimental malignant brain infarcts (Forsting, M. et al. 1995). Thereafter, clinical efficacy was shown in several clinical trials of malignant middle cerebral artery infarction (Vahedi, K. et al. 2007) . Recently, we investigated the effect of DC at varying time-points after ICH, induced by autologous blood injection in Wistar rats. DC performed up to 24 hours after ICH was proven beneficial in terms of reducing mortality and improving the neurological outcome (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009). In this study, we aimed to explore the effect of DC on MRI-related parameters (T_2 signal intensity, ADC) collected from the hematoma, perihematoma tissue, and the brain tissues in the ipsilateral cortical regions.

Perihematoma ROIs-penumbra

In the ICH-only group, no decreased rADC values were observed in the perihematoma regions. **Thus, we found no evidence of presumed perihematoma penumbra in the hyperacute phase (day 0).** This finding supports the claim from other experimental studies, which showed no ischemic perihematoma penumbra (Orakcioglu, B. et al. 2008; Qureshi, A. I. et al. 1999). Recently Zazulia and colleagues introduced a new concept, metabolic penumbra, on the basis of decreased oxygen utilization and increased glucose uptake in the perihematoma tissues (Zazulia, A. R. et al. 2009) However, these may be attributed to potential coexisting pathologies in ICH, including inflammation, seizure activity, spreading depression, or glutamate induced cytotoxicity (Vespa, P. M. 2009). Deciphering metabolic penumbra and its clinical and pathological consequences need further studying.

Perihematoma ROIs-edema

A significant difference in rADC values was observed on day 3, between ICH-1h and ICH only group. In addition, an increased r T_2 -SI was evident as hyperacute finding in perihematoma region, with further increase on day 3 in ICH-6h group. **Suggesting earlier craniectomy had more influence on diffusion parameter and edema.** Early increase in r T_2 -SI in all groups can be attributed to early development of perihematoma

edema. In animal models, edema has been noted to increase in several hours and peak around 3 to 4 days and decline gradually, resolving in approximately 2 weeks (Tomita, H. et al. 1994; Xi, G. et al. 1998; Yang, G. Y. et al. 1994). Edema evident on day 3 in all the groups could be due to the coagulation cascade and thrombin production and increased BBB permeability and increased sodium content resulting from increased RBC breakdown products (Xi, G. et al. 2006). Edema formation could be explained through either iron (potent catalyst of lipid peroxidation), a release of breakdown product of hemoglobin after erythrocytes lyse may contribute to BBB dysfunction (Xi, G. et al. 2001), or through direct damage to neurons and astrocytes involved in maintaining extracellular hemostasis (Matz, P. G. et al. 1997). This trend could be supported by a similar finding from Marinkovic and coworker's experiment (Marinkovic, I. et al. 2009), ICH volume at day 3 was significantly larger in the ICH-only group compared to all DC groups (Figure 9). Decreased ICH volume in DC groups could result in increased blood flow in perihematomal region. In the ICH-6h group, many animals had cerebral herniations (Figure 10) from the DC site probably because of maximum increase in ICP during that period (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 1999), which could have led to a traction to the hematomal and perihematomal tissues resulting in significant edema formation.

Cortical ROIs

In DC-only group, both rADC and rT₂-SI values remained unchanged during the follow-up in the cortical ROIs. This suggests that, our DC procedure did not induce tissue changes detectable with DWI or T₂-WI in the underlying cortex. In ICH-only group as well, rADC and rT₂-SI values of the cortical ROIs showed no change during the follow-up, **suggesting that hematoma, with its considerable volume in the striatum, leads to no MRI visible secondary injury in the cortex.** Compared to ICH-only group, rADC in the cortical ROI-c1 of the ICH-6h group and rADC in the cortical ROI-c2 of the both ICH-1h and ICH-6h groups were increased on day 3. However, no corresponding rT₂-SI changes were observed. This suggests that a different mechanism, rather than edema should be underlying these rADC increases in early DC groups on day 3. An explanation is that DC, at a time-point when intracranial pressure tends to increase (1 h) or already is maximum (6 h) (Qureshi, A. I. et al. 1999), leads to expansion of the ipsilateral hemisphere (Figure 11) towards the atmosphere and results in increased interstitial space and thus more freely movement of the protons;

consequently, rADC increases. Supporting this hypothesis, we observed herniations in most of the animals subjected to DC at 6 h (Figure 10). In addition there was no signal intensity change in the cortical region which may be because of no fluid extravasation from vascular compartment to interstitial compartment in cortical region suggesting no edema formation.

ROIs in the hematoma

To date, impact of DC on the composition of hematoma or on its temporal course has not been studied. In the present study therefore we evaluated temporal changes in the MRI characteristics of the hematoma following DC. Although a temporal change in rADC and rT₂-SI was observed in all the groups, none of these MRI parameters collected from inner hematomal regions showed changes due to the DC; in other words, **DC did not induce a significant effect on the dynamic composition of the hematoma.** However, we should note that in the autologous blood injection model uses coagulum formation and resorption of the hematoma is faster, than in clinical situation where bleeding of an intracranial vessel may continue hours and hematoma may grow over time (Strbian, D. et al. 2008). Therefore, in this study, we might have failed to mimic the potential therapeutic effect of the DC on the hematoma itself. A similar study to ours should be replicated using collagenase model of ICH, in which a more pronounced efficacy of DC may appear.

Given that, the earlier the DC is performed the better the outcome is; we suggest, increased perihematoma and increased cortical rADC values may be predictors of favorable outcome in ICH treated with DC.

Limitations

We evaluated the perihematoma region in two layers: the outer layer was detected visually as areas with increased signal. The inner layer was defined as a thinner ROI (of 0.5 mm-width), which underlied the outer one in close proximity to the hematoma. We used this approach thinking that any secondary ischemic change surrounding hematoma would occur in areas closest to hematoma and signal changes due to vasogenic edema would mask the changes in a theoretical penumbra. The mean values of rT₂-SI in the perihematoma inner ROI were usually lower than 0.9 suggesting that this ROI somehow included parts of the hematoma. The reason could be, while making the ROI

manually considerable precisions (visual interpretation) were taken not to include the hematoma region, but the accuracy cannot be validated because of ill-defined border between hematoma and normal tissue. So reliably we cannot comment on the results from the inner penumbra ROIs.

10. CONCLUSIONS

We found no MRI-based evidence of perihematomal ischemic penumbra in a rat ICH model followed by therapeutic DC. We also conclude that hematoma leads to no MRI-visible secondary injury in the cortex. DC performed earlier than 24 h induces MRI changes suggesting tissue expansion towards free space created by DC both in perihematomal tissues and the cortex. We observed no changes inside the hematoma in DC groups except for the same temporal changes with days of follow-up in all the ICH groups.

11. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study was carried out at the Department of Neurology, Helsinki University Central Hospital and Experimental MRI Laboratory, Biomedicum, Helsinki.

First of all I want to thank Docent Turgut Tatlisumak for giving me the opportunity to carry out my master's thesis in his group. It has been an honor to work with such a genius, hard-working, and humorous person who always have interesting information in his pocket to share to, and always keep his environ light. I owe my thanks to Daniel Strbian whose vital guidance led this work finish smoothly.

I warmly thank my colleagues especially Aysan Durukan for helping me strengthen my writing capabilities, Ivan Marinkovic and Eric Pedrono for teaching me the experimental techniques and for offloading my pressure with their humerous talks and lastly not least Usama Abo Ramadan for his guidance in MRI image analysis.

I would like to thank my sister Shama, my nephew and niece Devanshu and Anika for their love and patience while I was working. However my deepest and most sincere

thanks go to my beloved wife Roopsi for her continuous love and faith in me. Thank you mom and dad, without you I would have never dared to enter the field of research.

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